

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY AND BRAND TRUST ON THE DECISION TO PURCHASE WHEY PROTEIN EVOLENE PRODUCTS IN GYM MEMBERS IN GRESIK

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received Apr 10, 2024 Revised Apr 20, 2024 Accepted Apr 29, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Product Quality, Brand Trust, Purchasing Decisions</p>	<p>In contemporary times, a significant number of individuals possess knowledge on the significance of physical activity and have incorporated it into their everyday routines. This significantly influences the growth of the sports industry. Due to the rapid expansion of the sports industry, particularly in the fitness sector, there has been significant growth in the whey protein market. Individuals who engage in regular physical activity, particularly those who are members of fitness centres, require whey protein as a supplementary source of nutrition to fulfil their daily protein requirements. The whey protein sector presents a lucrative market opportunity for whey protein producers and companies, particularly Evolene. The objective of this study is to assess the impact of Product Quality (X1) and Brand Trust (X2) on the Purchasing Decisions (Y) of Evolene Whey Protein Products. This research is a quantitative study that focuses on the community of male consumers who use evolene whey protein in gyms in Gresik. 97 consumers at Surya Gym Members completed a survey using Google Form, providing feedback on their use of evolene whey protein. The research employed validity and reliability tests to assess the instruments. This study employed traditional assumption testing, including linearity tests, normalcy tests, and Multicollinearity tests. The analysis in this research employs statistical tests such as the t-test, F-test, and coefficient of determination test (R²), using the data analysis technique of multiple linear regression. The analysis of product quality and brand trust variables indicates that both variables, Product Quality and Brand Trust, have a positive and significant impact on the Purchasing Decision of Evolene Whey Protein Products for Gym Members in Gresik.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p> <div style="text-align: right;"> </div>

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INTRODUCTION

In this day and age, many people are aware that exercise is very important for body health and exercise has also become a lifestyle for people's lives. Gym members

have needs to get maximum results, such as adequate rest, nutritious food and of course whey protein. Whey Protein is a protein found in whey, which is the remaining milk produced in cheese production. This type of protein is widely used to increase muscle mass. There are whey protein brand products that have the same benefits as Evolene. Evolene is an Indonesian supplement brand that has received labdoor certification. Labdoor is America's #1 vitamin and supplement certification body. So this means that Evolene has been recognized for its safety and effectiveness internationally. Evolene also received a brand award as the best seller fitness supplement in Indonesia. Evolene even broke the world record for selling the most fitness supplements via a website in 1 hour (Fransiscus Harijanto & 2023, 2023). Evolene itself is a local product that has the best quality which of course has won many awards and has also gone international for world competitions. Producers are required to not only create products but also understand the desires and needs of consumers. The phenomenon published by IntipSeleb Lokal (Raizza 2023) on January 17 was that there were contents that did not match the labels printed on the packaging. Where, the results of the brand's supplement label claim stated that the whey protein contained 25 grams of protein, but it turned out that when checked in the lab, the results were only half that protein, namely 13 grams, which caused a lack of consumer confidence in the product. With this research the author took the case of the evolene product. Because it turns out that most of the gym members use Evolene products. Therefore, the author wants to delve into a form of research entitled The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Trust on Purchasing Decisions of Evolene Whey Protein Products among Gym Members in Gresik.

HYPOTHESIS

First Hypothesis:

- H₀: There is no influence of product quality on product purchasing decisions

Whey Protein Evolene

- H_a: There is an influence of product quality on purchasing decisions for Whey Protein Evolene products

Second Hypothesis:

- H₀: There is no influence of Brand Trust on Purchasing Decisions for Evolene Whey Protein Products

- Ha : There is an influence of Brand Trust on Product Purchasing Decisions *Whey Protein Evolene*

Third Hypothesis:

- H0: There is no influence of Product Quality and Brand Trust on Purchasing Decisions for Evolene Whey Protein Products
- Ha: There is an influence of product quality and brand trust on purchasing decisions for whey protein products.

METHODS

In this research, the approach used is descriptive quantitative, where research that describes variables as they are is supported by data in the form of numbers generated from the actual situation. The sampling method used in the research is probability sampling. Data collection was used using a questionnaire instrument and distributing the questionnaire offline and online. After the data used for research was collected, it was analyzed using the t test (partial test), F test (simultaneous), determination coefficient test (R²). This research was conducted at the Gym in Gresik. This research was conducted over a period of five months starting from February to June 2024. Data collection used was through offline and online questionnaires where respondents were given a list of statements that were in accordance with the research indicators, namely Product Quality, Brand Trust and Purchase Decisions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity test

		R count	R table	Conclusion
PRODUCT QUALITY (X1)	X1.1	0.659	0.361	Valid
	X1.2	0.624		Valid
	X1.3	0.679		Valid
	X1.4	0.602		Valid
	X1.5	0.63		Valid
<i>Brand Trust</i> (X2)	X2.1	0.636	0.361	Valid
	X2.2	0.727		Valid
	X2.3	0.681		Valid
	X2.4	0.582		Valid
	X2.5	0.497		Valid
	X2.6	0.604		Valid
Purchase Decision (Y)	Y1	0.723	0.361	Valid
	Y2	0.642		Valid
	Y3	0.707		Valid
	Y4	0.793		Valid

Source: Data processed by the author

With each indicator variable and based on the respondents' opinions, it can be declared valid. This can be seen from the results in the table above which proves that there is a calculated r value greater than the calculated r table for each claim element, namely 0.361.

Reliability Test

Based on the table below, it can be seen that the value of Cronbach's alpha for each variable is greater than 0.600. So it can be concluded that all the independent variables, namely Product Quality (X1), Brand Trust (X2) and the dependent variable with the Purchase Decision variable (Y) can be said to be all reliable or consistent variables.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Angka Pemandangan	Reliabel
Keputusan Pembelian (X1)	0,635	0,6	Reliable
Brand Trust (X2)	0,672	0,6	Reliable
Kualitas Produk (Y)	0,682	0,6	Reliable

Source: Data processed by the author

Normality test

The Normality Test is used to see whether the analyzed data is normal or not. The data is said to meet the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov formula. If the significance value is > 0.05, it can be said that the residuals are normally distributed.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.06575241
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.077
	Positive	.062
	Negative	-.077
Test Statistic		.077
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.149 ^c

Source: Data processed by the author

Based on the results of the table above, it is known that the significance value is 0.149 > 0.05, so it can be interpreted that this research has data that is normally distributed.

Linearity Test

Linearity Test means the first test carried out to evaluate whether the distribution of research data is linear or not. In this study, to determine the significance of the linearity test, it can be seen using deviation for linearity with a significance level of 0.05, so that the two variables must reach a significance value of > 0.05 to be considered to have a linear relationship.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
y * X1 Between Groups (Combined)	72.101	6	12.017	7.867	.000
Linearity	68.098	1	68.098	44.581	.000
Deviation from Linearity	4.003	5	.801	.524	.757
Within Groups	142.059	93	1.528		
Total	214.160	99			

Source: Data processed by the author

Based on the table above, the Deviation From Linearity value of the significance of the Product Quality variable with Purchasing Decisions is 0.757. These results show significance > 0.05 , so the relationship between variables is called linear, which means that the influence of the Product Quality variable (X1) and the Purchase Decision variable (Y) is linear.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
y * X2 Between Groups (Combined)	79.058	7	11.294	7.691	.000
Linearity	71.552	1	71.552	48.725	.000
Deviation from Linearity	7.506	6	1.251	.852	.533
Within Groups	135.102	92	1.468		
Total	214.160	99			

Source: Data processed by the author

The table above is the result of the Brand Trust Linearity test (X2). Based on the table above, the Deviation From Linearity value of the significance of the Brand Trust variable with Purchasing Decisions is 0.533. These results show significance > 0.05 , so the relationship between variables is called linear, which means that the influence of the Brand Trust variable (X2) and the Purchase Decision variable (Y) is linear.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test is seen from the tolerance value and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). If the VIF value < 10 , it means there is no multicollinearity. If the VIF value is > 10 then there is multicollinearity in the data.

		Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	3.309	1.743		1.898	.061		
	X1	.308	.095	.331	3.259	.002	.601	1.664
	X2	.279	.077	.369	3.637	.000	.601	1.664

a. Dependent Variable: y

Source: Data processed by the author

In the multicollinearity test, the tolerance values were found to be 0.601 and 0.601, so there were no values below 0.1. The VIF Variance Inflation Factor values obtained were 1.664 and 1.664, which are less than 10, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity in this study.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is used to test the feasibility or truth of the research hypothesis. The following are the results of the multiple linear regression test:

Table of Multiple Linear Regression Test results

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.309	1.743		1.898	.061
	KUALITAS PRODUK	.308	.095	.331	3.259	.002
	BRAND TRUST	.279	.077	.369	3.637	.000

a. Dependent Variable: KEPUTUSAN PEMBELIAN

Source: Data processed by the author

Used to see how much change in variable Y is due to an increase in variable X and is interpreted as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 3,309 + 0.308X_1 + 0.279X_2 + e$$

The test results above are as follows:

- a) The a value of 3.309 is a constant which if the variable value of Product Quality and Brand Trust is considered zero, then the Purchase Decision will increase by 3.902
- b) b1 (Regression coefficient X1) is 0.308. Proving that if there is an increase of 1 unit in the Product Quality variable, there will be an increase in the Purchasing Decision variable by 0.308.

- c) b2 (Regression coefficient X2) is 0.279. Proving that if there is an increase of 1 unit in the Brand Trust variable, there will be an increase in the Purchase Decision variable of 0.279.

Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

The Coefficient of Determination Test (R²) aims to show how much the Independent variable (X) contributes to the Dependent variable (Y)

Coefficient of Determination Test Results (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.632 ^a	.400	.387	1.151

Source: Data processed by the author

Based on the table above, the R² (R Square) figure is 0.400 or (40%). This shows that the percentage influence of Product Quality and Brand Trust on the Decision to Purchase Evolene Whey Protein Products for Gym Members in Gresik is 40%. In other words, the Purchasing Decision variable is influenced by the Product Quality and Brand Trust variables by 40%, while the remaining 100% -40% = 60% is influenced by the other independent variables studied. According to Ernawati in(Kotler and Keller, 2016)that product quality is an important factor that influences every customer's decision to buy a product. The better the quality of the product, the greater the interest of consumers who want to buy the product.

T test (partial)

The partial test or t test was carried out with the aim of proving the influence of the independent variables (Product Quality and Brand Trust) on the dependent variable (Purchasing Decision). The significance level of this research is 5% (0.05).

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.389	1.743		1.898	.061
	KUALITAS PRODUK	.388	.095	.331	3.259	.002
	BRAND TRUST	.279	.077	.369	3.637	.000

a. Dependent Variable: KEPUTUSAN PEMBELIAN

Source: Data processed by the author

To determine the t table is as follows:

$$T \text{ table} = t (\alpha/2 ; n - k - 1)$$

So in this study it can be seen that the significant value (α) is 5% (0.05) with the t table known to be 1.989. The results of hypothesis testing can be stated as follows:

1. First Hypothesis

H0: There is no influence of product quality on purchasing decisions for Whey Protein Evolene products

Ha: There is an influence of product quality on purchasing decisions for Whey Protein Evolene products

Obtained t count of 3.259, where t count > t table, namely (3.259 > 1.989) with a significance level of 0.002 < 0.05, so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. This shows that product quality influences purchasing decisions for Whey Protein Evolene products.

2. Second Hypothesis

H0: There is no influence of Brand Trust on Purchasing Decisions for Evolene Whey Protein Products.

Ha: There is an influence of Brand Trust on Purchasing Decisions for Evolene Whey Protein Products.

Obtained t count of 3.637, where t count > t table, namely (3.637 > 1.989) with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05, so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. This shows that Brand Trust influences the decision to purchase Evolene Whey Protein products.

TEST F (Simultaneous)

The F test (Simultaneous) is used to determine the simultaneous influence between the independent and dependent variables.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	85.624	2	42.812	32.308	.000 ^b
	Residual	128.536	97	1.325		
	Total	214.160	99			

a. Dependent Variable: KEPUTUSAN PEMBELIAN

b. Predictors: (Constant), BRAND TRUST, KUALITAS PRODUK

Source: Data processed by the author

F test results (Simultaneous) to find the F table value are as follows:

$$F \text{ table} = F(k ; n - k)$$

So the F table is known to be 3.09. The results of hypothesis testing can be stated as follows:

Hypothesis

Ho = Product Quality and Brand Trust have no influence on Purchasing Decisions for Evolene Whey Protein Products

Ha = Product Quality and Brand Trust influence the Purchase Decision for Evolene Whey Protein Products

From the table above, it can be seen that the calculated F is 32.308 while the F table is 3.09. So it can be concluded that $F_{count} > F_{table}$ and the significance value is 0.000. So in this research there is a simultaneous or joint influence of the Product Quality and Brand Trust variables which have a significant influence on the decision to purchase Whey Protein products.

CONCLUSION

This research has the characteristics of respondents among consumers who consume Evolene Whey Protein at the Gym in Gresik, including respondents whose average age is > 20 years - 30 years. The average respondent's job is as a private employee and the average respondent has a salary of > 2,000,000 - 3,000,000. Also, the average consumer has been consuming evolene whey protein for more than 6 months. Based on the results of the analysis of the independent variable, namely Product Quality, it shows significant results on Purchasing Decisions for Evolene Whey Protein Products. This is because the respondent's reference is that the evolene whey protein product has appropriate ingredients and product performance that has been recognized by many consumers. This greatly influences consumers in making purchasing decisions. Based on the results of the analysis of the relationship between the Product Quality and Brand Trust variables on Evolene Whey Protein Product Purchasing Decisions, it shows a very strong relationship. This is due to the high perception of product quality and brand trust in a product, which reflects the ease of consumers in making purchasing decisions for Evolene Whey Protein products.

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